

during final land preparation.

Regardless of method, 58 kg N/ha significantly improved panicles/m² and yield (see table). USG gave a grain yield advantage of 0.5 t/ha over PU. Differences among F, R, and M were

minimal.

Machine application increased yield 0.4-0.7 t/ha over broadcast split with PU at 58 kg N/ha. There was no difference between hand and machine

application methods with USG.

Placement of N fertilizer in the reduced zone as PU by machine or as USG by hand or machine gave higher agronomic efficiency. □

Effect of Zn and Cu on growth and nutrition of rice

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We studied the effect of soil application of Zn and Cu on dry matter yield and tissue concentration of Zn, Cu, Fe, Mn, and P in rice grown under submerged soil in a pot experiment in the greenhouse.

Soil was silty clay loam containing 20 ppm Olsen's P and DTPA extractable 0.64 ppm Zn, 0.46 ppm Cu, 11.6 ppm Fe, and 22.5 ppm Mn. Each pot contained 4.56 kg soil.

Basal nutrient application was 100 ppm N as urea, 26 ppm P as diammonium phosphate, and 25 ppm K as potassium chloride. Soil treatments were 0, 5, 10 and 20 ppm Zn and 0, 1, 2, and 5 ppm Cu as sulfates in a factorial combination with 2 replications.

Effect of Zn and Cu on dry matter yield of rice.

Effect of Zn and Cu on nutrient concentration in rice.^a

Nutrient levels (ppm)	Nutrient concentration									
	µg/g tissue				mg/g tissue					
	Zn		Cu		Fe		Mn		P	
	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R
Zn 0	50.8	59.0	27.0	31.6	0.40	4.66	0.20	0.57	1.12	1.30
Zn 5	56.3	60.8	25.4	30.7	0.40	4.40	0.20	0.66	1.02	1.15
Zn 10	69.3	67.6	24.8	28.1	0.40	4.06	0.20	0.75	1.00	1.26
Zn 20	73.7	72.8	20.5	24.1	0.34	3.44	0.19	0.64	0.90	1.26
Cu 0	73.4	73.6	21.5	25.1	0.40	4.49	0.20	0.55	1.11	1.16
Cu 1	62.6	67.6	21.9	29.7	0.38	3.55	0.19	0.67	1.00	1.00
Cu 2	62.6	60.5	26.6	28.6	0.40	4.47	0.20	0.62	0.99	1.28
Cu 5	51.6	58.6	27.8	31.1	0.36	4.02	0.20	0.78	0.95	1.53
LSD (0.05)	5.4	1.8	1.9	1.9	0.02	0.25	0.01	0.06	0.02	0.04

^a S = shoots, R = roots.

Five 20-d-old IR8 seedlings were transplanted in each of 32 pots, thinned to 3 plants/pot, and grown for 72 d. Additional 20 ppm N as urea was applied 40 d after transplanting.

Highest increase in dry matter yield was from 10 ppm Zn + 2 ppm Cu (see figure). Application of 5 ppm Zn + 1 or 2 ppm Cu also increased yield. The highest rates of Zn (20 ppm) + Cu (5 ppm) failed to increase dry matter yield.

Zn in roots and shoots increased with Zn application but decreased with Cu

application (see table). Cu in roots and shoots increased with Cu application but decreased with Zn application of 10 ppm or more. Fe in roots decreased at all Zn levels and at 1 and 5 ppm Cu. Fe in shoots decreased with 20 ppm Zn and 1 and 5 ppm Cu. Mn in roots increased with Zn and Cu; in shoots, it decreased with 20 ppm Zn and 1 ppm Cu. P in shoots decreased with Zn and Cu. In roots, it decreased at all Zn levels and at 1 ppm Cu. Application of 2 and 5 ppm Cu increased P in roots. □

Biofertilizer production of stem-cut planted and seeded *Sesbania rostrata*

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Although *S. rostrata* is a promising green manure species for lowland rice farming systems, production of seed and scarification may be a problem for

farmers. Vegetative propagation appears attractive because nodulation sites constitute primordia of adventive roots able to grow under waterlogged conditions.

We compared biofertilizer production by vegetative propagation through stem cuttings (30 and 20 cm) and broadcast seeding, at 3 plant densities.

The experiment May-June 1988 at IRRI farm was laid out in a randomized split-plot design with four replications.